

ISAC Receiver Design: Joint DoA and Data Estimation in the Presence of Incomplete Signal Observations

Iman Valiulahi, Christos Masouros, *Fellow*, IEEE, Mahmoud Alaaeldin, Emad Alsusa

Abstract—Integrated sensing and communication (ISAC) receiver design involves the challenge of jointly estimating the communication signal together with the direction of arrivals (DOAs) of the transmitters. This letter proposes an off-the-grid estimator for the ISAC receiver that jointly estimates the DOAs of K transmitters together with the communication data. We focus on the challenging case of incomplete observation, i.e., where only a subset of the received signals in space and time are available. We propose a convex optimization based on the dual of atomic norm minimization (ANM). Though the problem is non-deterministic polynomial time (NP)-hard, we leverage the Schur complement technique to develop semidefinite relaxations (SDRs) to implement it. Moreover, we study a fast algorithm based on the alternating direction method of multipliers (ADMM) technique. Finally, our numerical results explore the feasibility of the joint estimation with incomplete observations, while outperforming classical DOA estimators.

Index Terms—ISAC, atomic norm minimization, semidefinite relaxation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The main goal of the integrated sensing and communication (ISAC) receiver design is to unambiguously estimate the direction of arrivals (DOAs) and communication data of transmitters [1, 2]. Several approaches have been proposed for the classical DOA estimation problem, including Multiple Signal Classification (MUSIC) [3] and Estimating Signal Parameters via Rotational Invariance Techniques (ESPRIT) [4], which utilize the noise and signal subspaces, respectively. The performance of subspace decomposition methods, however, is significantly degraded in highly correlated or coherent target scenarios. They also rely on prior knowledge of the number of transmitters. Pioneered by [5], compressed sensing (CS) is considered a promising approach for DOA problems to reduce the implementation complexity and enhance the detection resolution by leveraging the signal sparsity in the spatial domain. In [6, 7], the authors showed that random antenna arrays can achieve almost the same performance with the uniform linear array (ULA) implementation. Nevertheless, this requires that the DOAs lie on a fine grid, which is not the case in practice as the DOAs can be located in any position in the target area. This mismatch between the inherent and estimated DOAs may degrade the reconstruction performance severely [8].

To overcome the above mismatch, an off-the-grid CS-based method named atomic norm minimization (ANM) was developed to promote the sparsity of the signal in a continuous dictionary. The ANM has been used in different

communication and signal processing problems such as MIMO radar [9], line spectral estimation [10], and impulsive noise elimination in OFDM system [11]. For example, in [9], the authors developed an ANM to estimate the spatial information of the radar channel in a continuous domain. From the communication perspective, estimating the transmit signal is essential to decode the digital messages. For this aim, the ANM is also used for blind detection [12, 13] where both the channel and transmit signal are simultaneously estimated. In [14], the authors proposed a regularized ANM for overlaid radar-communications systems.

As shown in Fig. 1, the receiver aims to jointly localize the DOAs of transmitters and their transmit data symbols from the received signal. In the classical DOA estimation problems, it is assumed that there are pilot signals, which help the receiver to estimate the channel between the transmitters and receivers. Then, the receiver can use this information to estimate parameters of interest in the next coherent time. Aside from practical scenarios where pilot signals might not be available, this assumption also wastes bandwidth and might reduce the estimation performance because of the demodulation error [15]. Hence, blind detection approaches are essential. The lifted ANM [12–14], as another blind estimator, requires precoding on the transmit signal, which significantly wastes bandwidth. Our proposed approach offers significant advantages over existing methods, such as the lifted ANM (LANM) framework presented in [13]. Specifically, while [13] is capable of detecting only a portion of the transmitted signal, our method enables the detection of all transmitted symbols, leading to significantly improved spectral efficiency. Moreover, our approach supports the detection of complex signals, which are crucial for practical communication systems employing QAM modulations, whereas [13] is limited to real signals. Unlike the semi-blind framework in [13], which depends on a predefined coding matrix known to the receiver, our method operates in a fully blind manner, eliminating the need for such prior information. Comparative results further demonstrate that our approach provides robust channel recovery performance and greatly enhances symbol detection capacity. These contributions underscore the practical relevance and scalability of our method in real-world scenarios.

In this letter, we propose a novel off-the-grid estimator via the dual of ANM, which does not require the pilot signal between the transmitters and receiver, prior information regarding the number of transmitters, and operate on a reduced transmit signal dimension. We present a joint DOAs and

Fig. 1: The system model.

communication data estimation problem using the dual of the ANM when only a random subset of received signal samples is observed. This relates to practical receiver implementations with reduced complexity, such as antenna selection [16], using randomly selected dictionary waveforms for the match filter or sub-Nyquist samples [17]. Moreover, this approach can be used for hybrid analog-beamforming architectures to reduce the implementation complexity and cost. The proposed problem requires an infinite-dimensional search over the spatial domain, therefore, it is difficult to solve. To tackle this, we leverage the results of the Schur complement approach to develop the semidefinite relaxations (SDR)s to implement the proposed problem. We then provide a fast algorithm based on the alternating direction methods of multiplexers (ADMM) to enhance the implementation time. Simulation results are done to investigate the performance of the proposed estimator and to demonstrate its superiority to the benchmarks.

The $\|\cdot\|_1$, $\|\cdot\|_2$, and $\|\cdot\|_\infty$ are ℓ_1 , ℓ_2 , and infinity norms, respectively. The Frobenius is shown by $\|\cdot\|_F$. The operators $\text{tr}(\cdot)$ and $(\cdot)^H$ are the trace of a matrix and hermitian of a vector, respectively. $\text{R}\{x\}$ denotes the real part of x .

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

We consider an ISAC receiver with N_r antennas to jointly estimate the DOAs of K transmitters and KP transmit signals, where P is the number of time slots, as shown in Fig. 1. The transmit signal can be written as $\mathbf{S} = [\mathbf{s}_1, \dots, \mathbf{s}_K]^T$ where $\mathbf{s}_k = [s_{k,1}, \dots, s_{k,P}]^T$. The received signal on the N_r -antenna receiver can be given by

$$\mathbf{Y} = \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k \bar{\mathbf{a}}(\theta_k) \mathbf{s}_k^T + \mathbf{N}, \quad \mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times P}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{N} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times P}$ is the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) with variance σ^2 for each entry and $\bar{\mathbf{a}}(\theta) = [1, e^{j\frac{2\pi d}{\lambda} \sin(\theta)}, \dots, e^{j\frac{(N_r-1)2\pi d}{\lambda} \sin(\theta)}]^T$ is the steering vector where θ_k is the DOA of the k -th transmitter. Moreover, $\alpha_k = |\alpha_k| e^{j\phi_k}$ is the k -th transmitter complex coefficient, that models the path loss together with the cross section. We assume $\lambda = 2d$ where λ and d are the wavelength and antenna spacing, respectively. Let us assume that there is only an incomplete observation of (1) as $\mathcal{P}_\Omega(\mathbf{Y})$, where $\mathcal{P}_\Omega(\cdot)$ is an orthogonal projection onto the linear space of

vectors supported on Ω , with the number of observations $M \leq N_r P$. Indeed, at the receiver side, we only observe M samples out of $N_r P$ at random. The problem is now to jointly estimate the transmitter parameters and the communication signals from the incomplete observation $\mathcal{P}_\Omega(\mathbf{Y})$. Inspired by [17] that studied matrix completion for MIMO radar, our incomplete observation model can be exploited in scenario where each receive antenna either performs matched filtering with a small number of randomly selected dictionary waveforms or obtains sub-Nyquist samples of the received signal, reducing implementation complexity and costs. Equation (1) contains PK unknown signal parameters, K unknown angles, K unknown α_k values, and K transmitters. This leads to a total of $PK + 3K$ unknown parameters overall, hence, it is difficult to solve with M observations. Below, we leverage the signal sparsity in the spatial domain and a simple coding on the ℓ_2 norm of the transmit signal.

III. THE DUAL OF ATOMIC NORM MINIMIZATION

This section aims to jointly estimate the DOAs of the transmitters and their transmit signals using the dual of the ANM when only a subset of observations is available. To do so, let us first bound the ℓ_2 norm of the transmit signal as $\|\mathbf{s}_k\|_2 = 1, \forall k$. Note that, as this is about of the norm of the signal vector instead of per-symbol, it does not exclude any signal constellations. Indeed, in our results, we explore non-constant modulus signaling, quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM) constellations. Then, we define the norm

$$\|\mathbf{X}\|_{\mathcal{A},0} := \inf \left\{ K : \mathbf{X} = \sum_{k=1}^K |\alpha_k| \mathbf{a}(\theta_k, \phi_k) \mathbf{s}_k^T, \right. \\ \left. \|\mathbf{s}_k\|_2 \leq 1, |\alpha_k| > 0, \|\boldsymbol{\alpha}\|_1 \leq 1 \right\}, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{a}(\theta, \phi) = [1, e^{j(\pi \sin(\theta) + \phi)}, \dots, e^{j((N_r-1)\pi \sin(\theta) + \phi)}]^T$. Detecting the transmitters' DOAs implicates finding the minimum K from the atomic decomposition of \mathbf{X} . Note that $\|\boldsymbol{\alpha}\|_1 \leq 1$ is required to bound the dual of the atomic norm in (9), which differs from the conventional atomic norm, as it aims only to estimate the DOAs using pilot signals. Thus, we define a relaxed convex version of $\|\mathbf{X}\|_{\mathcal{A},0}$ as

$$\|\mathbf{X}\|_{\mathcal{A}} := \inf \left\{ \|\boldsymbol{\alpha}\|_1 = \sum_k |\alpha_k| : \mathbf{X} = \sum_{k=1}^K |\alpha_k| \mathbf{a}(\theta_k, \phi_k) \mathbf{s}_k^T, \right. \\ \left. \|\mathbf{s}_k\|_2 \leq 1, |\alpha_k| > 0, \|\boldsymbol{\alpha}\|_1 \leq 1 \right\}. \quad (3)$$

Then, we propose the following penalized optimization

$$\min_{\mathbf{X}} \mu \|\mathbf{X}\|_{\mathcal{A}} + \frac{1}{2} \|\mathcal{P}_\Omega(\mathbf{Y}) - \mathbf{X}\|_F^2, \quad (4)$$

where $\mu > 0$ is a penalty parameter that balances the sparsity of the channel and power density of the noise. To recover the DOAs using the primal problem, an infinite-dimensional search over $[0, 2\pi)$, where the DOAs lie, is required. Specifically, $\theta_k \in [0, 2\pi)$ for all k . The primal problem is difficult to solve, and no SDR can be applied because the primal problem of the ANM is generally designed for cases where the transmit

signal is available in advance. However, we aim to estimate both the DOAs and the transmit signal simultaneously. To tackle this issue, we exploit the dual technique. To obtain the dual problem of the primal problem in (4), let us write the Lagrangian function as

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Q}) &= \mu \|\mathbf{X}\|_{\mathcal{A}} + \frac{1}{2} \|\mathcal{P}_{\Omega}(\mathbf{Y}) - \mathbf{X}\|_F^2 + \langle \mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{X} - \mathbf{X} \rangle \\ &= \|\mathbf{X}\|_{\mathcal{A}} \left(\mu - \frac{\text{R}\{\text{tr}(\mathbf{Q}^H \mathbf{X})\}}{\|\mathbf{X}\|_{\mathcal{A}}} \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} (\|\mathcal{P}_{\Omega}(\mathbf{Y}) - \mathbf{X}\|_F^2 + \text{R}\{\text{tr}(\mathbf{Q}^H \mathbf{X})\}),\end{aligned}\quad (5)$$

where $\langle \mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{X} \rangle = \text{R}\{\text{tr}(\mathbf{Q}^H \mathbf{X})\}$ in which $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times P}$ is the dual variable. It is worth noting that the third term of the first line, which is equal to zero, is added in order to obtain the dual problem. Regarding the duality theorem, the Lagrangian function must be minimized first with respect to \mathbf{X} . Thus, to avoid an unbounded solution for the first term of the Lagrangian function, the following constraint is required

$$\|\mathbf{Q}\|_{\mathcal{A}}^* = \sup_{\mathbf{X}} \frac{\text{R}\{\text{tr}(\mathbf{Q}^H \mathbf{X})\}}{\|\mathbf{X}\|_{\mathcal{A}}}\quad (6)$$

$$= \sup_{\|\mathbf{X}\|_{\mathcal{A}} \leq 1} \text{R}\{\text{tr}(\mathbf{Q}^H \mathbf{X})\} \leq \mu,\quad (7)$$

where $\|\mathbf{Q}\|_{\mathcal{A}}^*$ is known as the dual norm of the atomic norm. Using the first derivative of $\frac{1}{2} (\|\mathcal{P}_{\Omega}(\mathbf{Y}) - \mathbf{X}\|_F^2) + \text{R}\{\text{tr}(\mathbf{Q}^H \mathbf{X})\}$ with respect to \mathbf{X} , we can find the solution as $\mathbf{X}^* = \mathcal{P}_{\Omega}(\mathbf{Y}) - \mathbf{Q}$. Then, the dual problem can be given by

$$\begin{aligned}\min_{\mathbf{Q}} \quad & \|\mathcal{P}_{\Omega}(\mathbf{Y}) - \mathbf{Q}\|_F^2 \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \|\mathbf{Q}\|_{\mathcal{A}}^* \leq \mu, \mathbf{Q}_{\Omega^T} = 0,\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times P}$ is the optimization variable and Ω^T is the complementary set of Ω . The last constraint states that dual variable \mathbf{Q} must be equal to zero where there is no observation based on duality theory and optimization efficiency [18]. Indeed, when a certain observation does not contribute, the corresponding dual variable must be zero [18]. The atomic and Frobenius norms are convex. Additionally, there is no strictly explicit inequality constraint in the primal problem in (4), hence, Slater's condition holds, ensuring strong duality [19]. As a result, the solutions of the primal and dual problems coincide. Though problem (8) is convex, it is a non-deterministic polynomial time (NP)-hard problem because of the infinite-dimensional search over the spatial domain. Nevertheless, we resolve the mentioned issue using the SDR technique as follows.

A. DOA Estimation

Let us first write

$$\begin{aligned}& \sup_{\|\mathbf{X}\|_{\mathcal{A}} \leq 1} \text{R}\{\text{tr}(\mathbf{Q}^H \mathbf{X})\} \\ &= \sup_{\substack{\theta, \phi \in [0, 2\pi), \|\alpha\|_1 \leq 1 \\ \|\mathbf{s}_k\|_2 \leq 1}} \left\langle \sum_{k=1}^K |\alpha_k| \mathbf{a}(\theta_k, \phi_k) \mathbf{s}_k^T, \mathbf{Q} \right\rangle \\ &= \sup_{\substack{\theta, \phi \in [0, 2\pi), \|\alpha\|_1 \leq 1 \\ \|\mathbf{s}_k\|_2 \leq 1}} \sum_{k=1}^K |\alpha_k| \text{R}\{\mathbf{s}_k^T \mathbf{Q}^H \mathbf{a}(\theta_k, \phi_k)\} \\ &= \sup_{\theta, \phi \in [0, 2\pi), \|\alpha\|_1 \leq 1} \sum_{k=1}^K |\alpha_k| \|\mathbf{Q}^H \mathbf{a}(\theta_k, \phi_k)\|_2 \\ &= \sup_{\theta, \phi \in [0, 2\pi), \|\alpha\|_1 \leq 1} \|\mathbf{Q}^H \mathbf{a}(\theta, \phi)\|_2 \|\alpha\|_1 \\ &\leq \sup_{\theta, \phi \in [0, 2\pi)} \|\mathbf{Q}^H \mathbf{a}(\theta, \phi)\|_2.\end{aligned}\quad (9)$$

The third equality can be obtained using $\|\mathbf{s}_k\|_2 \leq 1$. The last equality is because of $\|\alpha\|_1 \leq 1$. To have $\|\mathbf{Q}\|_{\mathcal{A}}^* \leq \mu$, we use the Schure complement technique as $\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P} & \mathbf{Q} \\ \mathbf{Q}^H & \mu^2 \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \succeq 0$, where $\mathbf{P} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times N_r}$ is a hermitian matrix and \mathbf{I} is an identity matrix with size P . For any given \mathbf{t} , we can write $\mu^2 \mathbf{t}^H \mathbf{P} \mathbf{t} - \mathbf{t}^H \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{Q}^H \mathbf{t} \geq 0$, consequently, $\mu^2 \mathbf{t}^H \mathbf{P} \mathbf{t} \geq \|\mathbf{Q}^H \mathbf{t}\|_2^2$. Let us set $\mathbf{t} = \mathbf{a}(\theta, \phi)$, therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}\|\mathbf{Q}^H \mathbf{a}(\theta, \phi)\|_2^2 &\leq \mu^2 \mathbf{a}^H(\theta, \phi) \mathbf{P} \mathbf{a}(\theta, \phi) \\ &= \mu^2 \text{tr}(\mathbf{P} \mathbf{a}(\theta, \phi) \mathbf{a}^H(\theta, \phi)) \\ &\leq \mu^2 \|\mathbf{a}(\theta, \phi) \mathbf{a}^H(\theta, \phi)\|_{\infty} \|\mathbf{P}\|_1 \\ &= \mu^2 \|\mathbf{a}(\theta, \phi) \mathbf{a}^H(\theta, \phi)\|_{\infty} \text{tr}(\mathbf{P}),\end{aligned}\quad (10)$$

where the last equality comes from $\|\mathbf{P}\|_1 = \text{tr}(\mathbf{P})$ for semidefinite matrices. Observing that $\|\mathbf{a}(\theta, \phi) \mathbf{a}^H(\theta, \phi)\|_{\infty} = 1$ for all θ and ϕ , to have $\|\mathbf{Q}^H \mathbf{a}(\theta, \phi)\|_2^2 \leq \mu^2$, it is enough to have $\text{tr}(\mathbf{P}) \leq 1$ and $\text{tr}(\mathbf{Q} \Theta_k) = \delta_k$, where Θ_k is an elementary Toeplitz matrix with ones on its k -th diagonal and zeros elsewhere and $\delta_k = 1$ if $k = 0$, otherwise $\delta_k = 0$, $k \in \{1 - N_r, \dots, P - 1\}$. Therefore, the problem can be written in a tractable form as

$$\begin{aligned}\min_{\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{P}} \quad & \|\mathcal{P}_{\Omega}(\mathbf{Y}) - \mathbf{Q}\|_F^2 \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \text{tr}(\mathbf{Q} \Theta_k) = \delta_k, \forall k, \\ & \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P} & \mathbf{Q} \\ \mathbf{Q}^H & \mu^2 \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \succeq 0, \\ & \mathbf{Q}_{\Omega^T} = 0, \text{tr}(\mathbf{P}) \leq 1.\end{aligned}\quad (11)$$

The DOAs can be detected as the peaks of polynomial $\|(\mathbf{Q}^*)^H \mathbf{a}\|_2^2$, where \mathbf{Q}^* is the solution of problem (11), that achieve $\sqrt{\mu}$ as shown in Fig. 2 (a) that we will discuss in the following. The relaxation used in problem (8) may differ from the original dual solution due to approximations for computational tractability. However, it performs well in practice, as shown in our simulations, especially in Fig. 2(b), which shows that the dual polynomial obtained from the relaxed dual problem can be perfectly localize the DoAs of the targets, and in prior works [18, 20, 21].

Algorithm 1: The ADMM algorithm for problem (12).

1: Let us initialize

$$\mathbf{Q}^0 = \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{P}^0 = \mathbf{0}, \boldsymbol{\psi}^0 = \mathbf{0}, \rho^0 = 0, \boldsymbol{\Delta}^0 = \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{S}^0 = \mathbf{0},$$

$$\xi = 0.5, \text{ and set } t = 0 : T \text{ as the iteration step.}$$

2: **Repeat**

3: Update \mathbf{Q}^{t+1} , \mathbf{P}^{t+1} , and \mathbf{W}^{t+1} , following (17) and (19).

4: Update $\boldsymbol{\Delta}^{t+1}$, $\boldsymbol{\psi}^{t+1}$, and ρ^{t+1} , following (20).

5: Use $\|(\mathbf{Q}^*)^H \mathbf{a}\|_2^2 = \mu$ to estimate the DOAs and solve the LS problem and use $\frac{\mathbf{f}_k^*}{|\alpha_k|}$ to recover transmit signals.

B. Communication Data Estimation

By defining $\mathbf{f}_k = |\alpha_k| \mathbf{s}_k^T$, we can solve the following problem $\min_{\mathbf{f}_k, \forall k} \|\mathcal{P}_\Omega(\mathbf{Y}) - \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{a}(\theta_k^*) \mathbf{f}_k\|_F^2$, to estimate $\mathbf{f}_k, \forall k$ where θ_k^* is the estimated DOA for the k -th transmitter. Then, exploiting the fact that $\|\mathbf{s}_k\|_2 = 1$, we can estimate both \mathbf{s}_k and $|\alpha_k|$. The problem is an LS problem with the closed-form solution $\mathbf{A}^\dagger \mathcal{P}_\Omega(\mathbf{Y})$ where \mathbf{A}^\dagger is the pseudo-inverse of \mathbf{A} in which $\mathbf{A} = [\mathbf{a}(\theta_1^*), \dots, \mathbf{a}(\theta_K^*)]$.

C. Computational Complexity

The interior point method with the Newton step in CVX [22] entails a computational complexity in the order of $\mathcal{O}((E+F)^{1.6} E^2)$, where E and F are the numbers of variables and constraints, respectively. Problem (11) includes $N_r^2 + N_r P$ variables and $3N_r + 3P$ constraints, hence, the total computational costs can be approximated by $\mathcal{O}(N_r^{5.2} + (N_r P)^{3.6})$. This problem can be implemented for the moderate number of antennas and snapshots, however, for large-dimensional case, its computational complexity is prohibitive. Thus, in the next section, we provide an iterative algorithm based on the ADMM technique to expedite the implementation of (11).

IV. FAST ISAC ESTIMATION VIA ADMM

Let us first rewrite problem (11) as

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{P}} \quad & \|\mathcal{P}_\Omega(\mathbf{Y}) - \mathbf{Q}\|_F^2 \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \text{tr}(\mathbf{Q}\boldsymbol{\Theta}_k) = \delta_k, \forall k, \\ & \mathbf{W} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P} & \mathbf{Q} \\ \mathbf{Q}^H & \mu^2 \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{W} \succeq 0, \\ & \mathbf{Q}_{\Omega^c} = \mathbf{0}, \text{tr}(\mathbf{P}) \leq 1, \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{C}^{(N_r+P) \times (N_r+P)}$ is an auxiliary variable. Then, we can write the augmented Lagrangian function as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{Q}, \boldsymbol{\psi}, \rho, \mathbf{P}, \boldsymbol{\Delta}, \mathbf{W}) &= \|\mathcal{P}_\Omega(\mathbf{Y}) - \mathbf{Q}\|_F^2 + \sum_{k=-L}^L \psi_k (\text{tr}(\mathbf{Q}\boldsymbol{\Theta}_k) - \delta_k) + \rho(1 - \text{tr}(\mathbf{P})) \\ &+ \left\langle \boldsymbol{\Delta}, \mathbf{W} - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P} & \mathbf{Q} \\ \mathbf{Q}^H & \mu^2 \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \right\rangle + \xi \left\| \mathbf{W} - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P} & \mathbf{Q} \\ \mathbf{Q}^H & \mu^2 \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \right\|_F^2, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where $\xi > 0$ is a penalty parameter and $\boldsymbol{\psi} = \{\psi_k\}_{k=-L}^L$ are real scalars, $\rho \geq 0$, and $\boldsymbol{\Delta} \in \mathbb{C}^{(N_r+P) \times (N_r+P)}$ is a Hermitian matrix, i.e., $\boldsymbol{\Delta} = \boldsymbol{\Delta}^H$.

The ADMM includes the following iterative steps with iteration t as

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{Q}^{t+1}, \mathbf{P}^{t+1}) &= \min_{\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{P}} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{P}, \boldsymbol{\psi}^t, \rho^t, \boldsymbol{\Delta}^t, \mathbf{W}^t), \\ \mathbf{W}^{t+1} &= \min_{\mathbf{W} \succeq 0} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{Q}^{t+1}, \mathbf{P}^{t+1}, \boldsymbol{\psi}^t, \rho^t, \boldsymbol{\Delta}^t), \\ \boldsymbol{\Delta}^{t+1} &= \boldsymbol{\Delta}^t + \xi \left(\mathbf{W}^{t+1} - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P}^{t+1} & \mathbf{Q}^{t+1} \\ (\mathbf{Q}^{t+1})^H & \mu^2 \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \right), \\ (\boldsymbol{\psi}^{t+1}, \rho^{t+1}) &= \min_{\boldsymbol{\psi}, \rho} \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\psi}, \rho, \mathbf{Q}^{t+1}, \mathbf{P}^{t+1}, \boldsymbol{\Delta}^{t+1}, \mathbf{W}^{t+1}). \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Let us first define

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\Delta}^t &:= \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\Delta}_1^t \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times N_r} & \boldsymbol{\Delta}_2^t \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times P} \\ (\boldsymbol{\Delta}_2^H)^t & \boldsymbol{\Delta}_3^t \in \mathbb{C}^{P \times P} \end{bmatrix}, \\ \mathbf{W}^t &:= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{W}_1^t \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times N_r} & \mathbf{W}_2^t \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times P} \\ (\mathbf{W}_2^H)^t & \mathbf{W}_3^t \in \mathbb{C}^{P \times P} \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Then, we can write the following derivatives as

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{\mathbf{Q}} &= \mathcal{P}_\Omega(\mathbf{Y}) + 2\mathbf{Q}^H + \sum_{l=1}^L \boldsymbol{\Theta}_k + (\boldsymbol{\Delta}_2^H)^t + (\boldsymbol{\Delta}_3^H)^t \\ &\quad - 2(\mathbf{W}_2^H)^t - 2(\mathbf{W}_3^H)^t + 2\mu^2 \mathbf{Q}^H, \\ \nabla_{\mathbf{P}} &= -\rho \mathbf{I} - (\boldsymbol{\Delta}_1^H)^t - 2\xi(\mathbf{W}_1^H)^t + \mathbf{P} + \mathbf{Q}^t, \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

constrained on $\mathbf{Q}_{\Omega^c} = \mathbf{0}$. Therefore, the closed-form solutions can be obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} (2 + 2\mu^2)(\mathbf{Q}^H)^{t+1} &= -\mathcal{P}_\Omega(\mathbf{Y}) + 2(\mathbf{W}_2^H)^t + 2(\mathbf{W}_3^H)^t \\ &\quad - \sum_{l=1}^L \boldsymbol{\Theta}_k - (\boldsymbol{\Delta}_2^H)^t - (\boldsymbol{\Delta}_3^H)^t, \\ \mathbf{P}^{t+1} &= \rho \mathbf{I} + (\boldsymbol{\Delta}_1^H)^t + 2\xi(\mathbf{W}_1^H)^t - \mathbf{Q}^{t+1}. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

To update \mathbf{W} , we can write

$$\mathbf{W}^{(t+1)} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P}^{t+1} & \mathbf{Q}^{t+1} \\ (\mathbf{Q}^{t+1})^H & \mu^2 \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} - \frac{\boldsymbol{\Delta}^{(t)}}{2\xi}. \quad (18)$$

We then project $\mathbf{W}^{(t+1)}$ onto the positive semidefinite cone ($\mathbf{W} \succeq 0$) by computing its eigenvalue decomposition as below

$$\mathbf{W}^{(t+1)} = \mathbf{U} \text{diag}(\max(\boldsymbol{\lambda}, 0)) \mathbf{U}^H, \quad (19)$$

where \mathbf{U} and $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ are the eigenvectors and eigenvalues of $\mathbf{W}^{(t+1)}$. Finally, to update $\boldsymbol{\Delta}$, $\boldsymbol{\psi}$ and ρ , we can write

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\Delta}^{t+1} &= \boldsymbol{\Delta}^t + \xi \left(\mathbf{W}^{(t+1)} - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P}^{t+1} & \mathbf{Q}^{t+1} \\ (\mathbf{Q}^{t+1})^H & \mu^2 \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \right), \\ \psi_k^{t+1} &= \psi_k^t + \rho (\text{tr}(\mathbf{Q}\boldsymbol{\Theta}_k) - \delta_k), \\ \rho^{t+1} &= \rho^t + \lambda (1 - \text{tr}(\mathbf{P})). \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The procedure of the ADMM algorithm is summarized in Algorithm 1. After obtaining the Lagrangian variables using Algorithm 1, one can use $\|(\mathbf{Q}^*)^H \mathbf{a}\|_2^2 = \mu$ to recover DOAs and solve the LS problem and use $\frac{\mathbf{f}_k^*}{|\alpha_k|}$ to estimate the communication data. The computational complexity of the proposed algorithm is determined by the updates of key variables in

Fig. 2: The dual polynomial for the proposed JOG estimator and conventional ANM in Figs. 2 (a) and (b), respectively. The DOAs and $\sqrt{\mu}$ are shown by the dashed blue and red lines.

the optimization process. The update of \mathbf{Q} involves solving a linear system, which typically has a complexity of $\mathcal{O}(N_r P)$. Similarly, the update of \mathbf{P} also requires solving a linear system with a complexity of $\mathcal{O}(P)$. The update of \mathbf{W} , is generally considered to have a complexity of $\mathcal{O}((N_r + P)^3)$, as it involves matrix updates and calculations related to the block structure of \mathbf{W} and eigenvalue decomposition. The update of the dual variables ψ and ρ involves solving a relatively simple optimization problem, with a typical complexity of $\mathcal{O}(N_r + P)$, since the updates are based on solving for scalars in the dual problem. Lastly, the update of Δ has a computational complexity of $\mathcal{O}(N_r P)$. Assuming the optimization has T iterations, the total complexity will be dominated by the matrix operations for updating \mathbf{Q} , \mathbf{P} , \mathbf{W} , and the dual variables as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{O}(T \cdot (3N_r P + N_r + 2P + (N_r + P)^3)) \\ & \approx \mathcal{O}(T \cdot (N_r + P)^3) \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

This is less than the total complexity of problem (11), which means that the proposed fast algorithm can be used for high dimensional signaling.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we investigate the performance of the proposed joint off-the-grid (JOG) estimator via 1000 Monte-Carlo simulations. The DOAs of the transmitters are independently generated. We set $N_r = P = 10$. We define the root mean square error (RMSE) as $\text{RMSE} := \sqrt{\frac{1}{KN_{mc}} \sum_{n_{mc}=1}^{N_{mc}} \sum_{k=1}^K (\theta_{n_{mc},k} - \theta_{n_{mc},k}^*)^2}$, where N_{mc} is the number of Monte Carlo simulations and $\theta_{n_{mc},k}^*$ is the estimated DOA at the k -th transmitter for the n_{mc} -th simulation. We also define the symbol error rate (SER), $\text{SER} = \frac{1}{N_{mc}} \sum_{n_{mc}=1}^{N_{mc}} \mathbb{I}(S_{n_{mc}} - S_{n_{mc}}^*)$ where \mathbb{I} is a binary indicator such that $\mathbb{I} = 0$ if $S_{n_{mc}} = S_{n_{mc}}^*$, otherwise, $\mathbb{I} = 1$, in which $S_{n_{mc}}^*$ is the estimated signal at the n_{mc} -th simulation. We set $\mu = 0.6$. The QAM signaling is adapted from [23]. The value of ξ is crucial for balancing convergence speed and

Fig. 3: The RMSE of the DOA of the proposed estimator and benchmarks in Fig. 3.

stability in the augmented Lagrangian. In our simulations, we set $\xi = 0.5$, as it provided a good trade-off, ensuring efficient convergence without compromising stability, which is essential for the practical application of the algorithm. To ensure a fair comparison with the LANM framework outlined in [13], we modified the evaluation setup by increasing the number of time slots used to sample the received signal. This adjustment allowed both approaches to detect the same number of symbols, enabling a direct performance comparison.

We compare the dual polynomial of the proposed JOG estimator with the conventional ANM. For the conventional ANM, we implemented problem (11) without the third constraint. The transmit signal for the conventional ANM is required, however, our proposed estimator is able to recover the DOAs without prior knowledge of the transmit signal. This can be seen in Fig. 2 where the peaks of the dual polynomial for

Fig. 4: The SER of the proposed estimator and benchmarks in Fig. 4.

Fig. 5: The empirical rate of success of detecting all the DOAs from $M = 50$ to $M = N_r P = 100$ in Fig. 5.

our proposed estimator are exactly reached $\sqrt{\mu}$, however, the conventional ANM has many peaks, hence, it can not detect the DOAs.

We compare the performance of the DOA and transmit signal estimations. In Fig. 3, we plot the RMSE of DOA estimation in degree (deg) versus the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). We use the Cramér-Rao lower bound (CRLB) [24] as a performance bound. The proposed JOG estimator outperforms the conventional benchmarks and its performance is comparable to the CRLB. The results, presented in Fig. 3, demonstrate that our proposed method achieves comparable NMSE and SER performance to LANM while retaining its inherent advantages, such as fully blind estimation, the ability to handle complex signals, and the capability to detect a greater number of symbols for a given transmitted signal.

Once DOAs are detected, we implement the LS problem to recover the transmitted signal. We compare the SER of the proposed JOG estimator with the benchmarks. As shown in Fig. 4, the performance of the proposed estimator is better than the conventional approaches. It is observed from this

Fig. 6: The execution time versus the number of antennas, N_r , in Fig. 6.

figure that by enlarging the QAM constellation, the SER increases. Note that, to ensure a fair comparison with [13], we increased the number of time slots used to sample the signal. This demonstrates the advantage of our proposed approach in detecting more symbols from the same transmitted signal.”

We evaluate the empirical rate of success of detecting the DOAs in Fig. 5. We carry out the optimization problem for the different numbers of transmitters, and received samples from $M = 50$ to $M = N_r P = 100$. The pure white and black are related to the successful and unsuccessful recoveries for all the Monte-Carlo simulations, respectively. It is observed from this figure that for higher ratios of observations over numbers of transmitters the proposed JOG obtains a high success rate, while this declines with the increase of targets w.r.t. the numbers of observations.

Finally, Fig. 6 compares the execution time in seconds (s) versus the number of antennas for implementing the proposed estimator with conventional approaches using an Intel Core i7-6700, 2.6 GHz CPU computer. As shown in the figure, the proposed estimator outperforms the ANM in terms of execution time due to the ADMM algorithm.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

We studied an off-the-grid estimator for the ISAC systems in the case of an incomplete observation model. We proposed SDPs for implementing it. We then leveraged the ADMM technique to propose a fast algorithm for solving it. Simulation results evaluated the performance of the proposed estimator. Our proposed method focuses on a line-of-sight (LOS) propagation scenario. However, extending our approach to the multipath scenario would be an interesting research direction.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This paper is funded by the 6G MUSICAL project, which has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program (Grant Agreement No. 101139176 or UKRI Grant 10093329) and is co-funded by the European Union.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Liu, C. Masouros, A. P. Petropulu, H. Griffiths, and L. Hanzo, "Joint radar and communication design: Applications, state-of-the-art, and the road ahead," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 68, no. 6, pp. 3834–3862, 2020.
- [2] I. Valiulahi, C. Masouros, and A. Salem, "Net-zero energy dual-functional radar-communication systems," *IEEE Transactions on Green Communications and Networking*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 356–369, 2023.
- [3] R. Schmidt, "Multiple emitter location and signal parameter estimation," *IEEE transactions on antennas and propagation*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 276–280, 1986.
- [4] Y. Yan, J. Cai, and W.-Q. Wang, "Two-stage esprit for unambiguous angle and range estimation in fda-mimo radar," *Digital Signal Processing*, vol. 92, pp. 151–165, 2019.
- [5] M. A. Herman and T. Strohmer, "High-resolution radar via compressed sensing," *IEEE transactions on signal processing*, vol. 57, no. 6, pp. 2275–2284, 2009.
- [6] Y. Yu, A. P. Petropulu, and H. V. Poor, "Mimo radar using compressive sampling," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 146–163, 2010.
- [7] M. Rossi, A. M. Haimovich, and Y. C. Eldar, "Spatial compressive sensing in mimo radar with random arrays," in *2012 46th Annual Conference on Information Sciences and Systems (CISS)*. IEEE, 2012, pp. 1–6.
- [8] Y. Chi, L. L. Scharf, A. Pezeshki, and A. R. Calderbank, "Sensitivity to basis mismatch in compressed sensing," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 59, no. 5, pp. 2182–2195, 2011.
- [9] W.-G. Tang, H. Jiang, and Q. Zhang, "Range-angle decoupling and estimation for fda-mimo radar via atomic norm minimization and accelerated proximal gradient," *IEEE Signal Processing Letters*, vol. 27, pp. 366–370, 2020.
- [10] I. Valiulahi, S. Daei, F. Haddadi, and F. Parvaresh, "Two-dimensional super-resolution via convex relaxation," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 67, no. 13, pp. 3372–3382, 2019.
- [11] I. Valiulahi, F. Parvaresh, and A. A. Beheshti, "Eliminating impulsive noise in pilot-aided ofdm channels via dual of penalized atomic norm," *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 23, no. 11, pp. 2059–2062, 2019.
- [12] M. Bigdeli, H. Fathi, I. Valiulahi, and C. Masouros, "Non-coherent ofdm transmission via off-the-grid joint channel and data estimation," *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, 2022.
- [13] S. Sayyari, S. Daei, and F. Haddadi, "Blind two-dimensional super-resolution in multiple-input single-output linear systems," *IEEE Signal Processing Letters*, vol. 28, pp. 583–587, 2020.
- [14] E. Vargas, K. V. Mishra, R. Jacome, B. M. Sadler, and H. Arguello, "Dual-blind deconvolution for overlaid radar-communications systems," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2208.04381*, 2022.
- [15] L. Zheng and X. Wang, "Super-resolution delay-doppler estimation for ofdm passive radar," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 65, no. 9, pp. 2197–2210, 2017.
- [16] I. Valiulahi, C. Masouros, A. Salem, and F. Liu, "Antenna selection for energy-efficient dual-functional radar-communication systems," *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 741–745, 2022.
- [17] S. Sun, W. U. Bajwa, and A. P. Petropulu, "Mimo-mc radar: A mimo radar approach based on matrix completion," *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, vol. 51, no. 3, pp. 1839–1852, 2015.
- [18] G. Tang, B. N. Bhaskar, P. Shah, and B. Recht, "Compressed sensing off the grid," *IEEE transactions on information theory*, vol. 59, no. 11, pp. 7465–7490, 2013.
- [19] S. Boyd, "Convex optimization," *Cambridge UP*, 2004.
- [20] Y. Chi and Y. Chen, "Compressive two-dimensional harmonic retrieval via atomic norm minimization," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 63, no. 4, pp. 1030–1042, 2015.
- [21] Y. Chi, "Guaranteed blind sparse spikes deconvolution via lifting and convex optimization," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 782–794, 2016.
- [22] M. Grant and S. Boyd, "Cvx: Matlab software for disciplined convex programming, version 2.1," 2014.
- [23] J. G. Proakis and M. Salehi, *Digital communications*. McGraw-hill New York, 2001, vol. 4.
- [24] P. Chen, Z. Chen, Z. Cao, and X. Wang, "A new atomic norm for doa estimation with gain-phase errors," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 68, pp. 4293–4306, 2020.